

Burial history and hydrocarbon generation model of the Lower–Middle Jurassic sediments in the Tarnovo depression

Nikola Botoucharov

Department of Geology, Paleontology and Fossil Fuels, Faculty of Geology and Geography, Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, 15 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd., 1504 Sofia, Bulgaria; e-mail: botnd@gea.uni-sofia.bg

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Abstract. This study deals with the geodynamic evolution in the Tarnovo depression, contributes to a better understanding of the burial and thermal history, and gives a model of the generation of hydrocarbons from the Lower–Middle Jurassic rocks. The implications of the complex heat flow scenario for the timing of hydrocarbon generation from the Stefanets Member of the Etropole Formation in selected sections were also analyzed. The Tarnovo depression is defined as a small tectonic unit in the central part of the South Moesian Platform margin developed mainly during the Early–Middle Jurassic. Therefore, the sediment subsidence during the Early–Middle Jurassic is largely a consequence of the tectonic processes in an extensional basin with tilted, fault-bounded, and eventually rotated blocks. There is a trend of increasing tectonic and basin subsidence in southern direction, observed in modeled well sections. The Lower–Middle Jurassic rocks enter the “oil window” in the late Barremian, Hauterivian, or even the late Valanginian towards the south, starting active generation in the middle Aptian. The model shows that gas generation is possible only in the southern and marginal zones of the Tarnovo depression. Among the sequence, the Stefanets Member of the Etropole Formation (Aalenian–early Bajocian in age), composed of shales and siltstones, possesses source rock qualities and good hydrocarbon generation potential. The research model argues for peak of the oil generation from the Stefanets Member at the end of the Barremian up to the Albian to the north and gas generation starting in the Barremian and continuing during the Cenozoic only in the southern part.

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INTRODUCTION

Numerous oil, gas, and gas-condensate fields and shows have been discovered in the Mesozoic and Cenozoic sedimentary formations located mainly in the Moesian Platform and its southern marginal zone, the South Moesian Platform margin (Fig. 1). The petroleum exploration in the Tarnovo depression, located in the central part of the South Moesian Platform margin, took place at the end of the 1970s and in the 1980s (Georgiev and Botoucharov,

2007). The main target was the thick Lower–Middle Jurassic succession, which in the central southern part of the study area is up to 800 m (Fig. 2). Over the next 20 years, fifteen exploratory wells were drilled in the Tarnovo depression, which found mostly gas and a few oil occurrences of no economic significance. These are water-dissolved nitrogen-methane gas and oil stains indicative of hydrocarbon migration processes. Nevertheless, the shales and clayey-carbonates from the marine Lower–Middle Jurassic sequence, in the southern

part of the Moesian Platform, have high organic matter content and a fair to very good hydrocarbon generation potential (Georgiev and Dabovski, 1997; Georgiev, 2000). These sediments have also been considered as source rocks for the discovered oil and gas-condensate fields in North Bulgaria (Georgiev, 2000, 2007). The comprehensive geological and geophysical investigations show that the Lower–Middle Jurassic deposits were buried at a depth of 2500–3800 m, which argue for optimal hydrocarbon generation perspectives.

The main purpose of this paper is to achieve better understanding of the burial and thermal history of the Lower–Middle Jurassic rocks in the Tarnovo depression. The implications of the tectonic and basin subsidence and complex heat flow scenario for the timing of hydrocarbon generation from the Stefanets Member of the Etropole Formation in selected sections were analyzed in detail as well.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The territory of Bulgaria is located on the European continental margin and covers part of the northern periphery of the Alpine orogen (Balkanides) and its foreland – the Moesian Platform (Georgiev and Botoucharov, 2007; Fig. 1). The Moesian Platform is composed of relatively undeformed Mesozoic successions with thicknesses up to 4–5 km, resting unconformably upon a gently folded Paleozoic basement and buried beneath Paleogene, Neogene,

and Quaternary deposits. The entire pile with Paleozoic and Mesozoic–Paleogene rocks is massive, up to 10–12 km near the Balkan thrust-fold belt.

The Mesozoic–Cenozoic evolution of the Moesian Platform margin was governed by geodynamic processes in the northern Peri-Tethyan shelf system (Georgiev and Dabovski, 1997; Georgiev *et al.*, 2001). The southern part of the platform was repeatedly affected by north–south-directed intra-continental extensions and failed rifting cycles during the Late Permian–Early Triassic, Late Triassic, Early Jurassic, and Late Cretaceous. These cycles were interrupted and followed by compressional events, which caused strong platform margin shortening, ultimately overprinted by the Alpine orogeny (Georgiev and Dabovski, 2000). The mid-Cretaceous and mid-Eocene compressions resulted in the formation of the Balkan thrust belt over the southern edge of the Moesian Platform (Georgiev and Botoucharov, 2007). The South Moesian Platform margin started formation during the Early–Middle Jurassic and is characterized by a complex, deepening to the south monocline structure composed of thick and shallow to deeper-water deposits.

The Tarnovo depression is defined as a small tectonic unit in the central part of the South Moesian Platform margin developed mainly during the Early–Middle Jurassic (Georgiev and Dabovski, 1997). The sedimentation lasted until the late Bathonian, when the Mid-Cimmerian orogeny culminated (Georgiev *et al.*, 2001). The lithostratigraphy

Fig. 1. Tectonic map of North Bulgaria with the main tectonic units and modeled well sections (after Zagorchev and Dabovski, 2009, with modifications).

Stratigraphy			Lithology	Thickness (m)	
Age	Formation	Member			
Middle Jurassic	Bathonian	Esenitsa		0–140	
		Polaten		15–120	
		Bov			
	Bajocian	Etropole	Shipkovo		
			Lopyan		80–250
			Stefanets		20–60
Aalenian	Ozirovo	Suhindol		10–130	
Hettangian–Toarcian		Bukorovtzi		20–65	
		Dolni Lukovit		0–110	
		Kostina		0–30	
	Bachiishte		0–20		

Fig. 2. Generalized lithostratigraphy of the Lower–Middle Jurassic sequence in the Tarnovo depression.

of the Lower–Middle Jurassic sequence in the Tarnovo depression is demonstrated in Fig. 2.

Lower Jurassic sedimentation began in the Hettangian?–Sinemurian with thin, very shallow-water clastic deposits of the Bachiishte and Kostina formations (Fig. 2). The Pliensbachian–early Aalenian sedimentation is recorded by the mainly shallow-marine Ozirovo Formation, which consists of two carbonate units – the Dolni Lukovit and Suhindol members, separated by the clayey-silty Bukorovtzi Member (Georgiev and Botoucharov, 2007). The overlying Etropole Formation is also heterogeneous and comprises three units – the lower Stefanets and the upper Shipkovo members are dominated by shale, whereas the middle Lopyan Member is mostly sandy, especially in its upper part. The shale-dominated Stefanets Member changes slowly upwards through irregular interbedding of shale and siltstones, and becomes dominated by coarse sandstones in the upper part of the Lopyan Member. This gradual facies transition records a shallowing

of the depositional environment. The late Bajocian–early Bathonian sedimentary record is dominated by shales of the Shipkovo Member and marlstones of the Bov Formation, which marks some deepening in the depositional environment. During the late Bathonian, the basin became very shallow, which resulted in the deposition of the sandy limestones of the Polaten Formation, grading northeastward into the thin silty shales of the Esenitsa Formation.

Within the Lower–Middle Jurassic sequence, the Ozirovo and Etropole formations are the thickest and have the longest stratigraphic extents (Georgiev, 1983; Sapunov and Tchoumatchenco, 1987). The geological and depositional settings in the Tarnovo depression during the late Aalenian–early Bajocian were favorable for the accumulation of deeper-water sediments, including mainly shales of the Stefanets Member (Georgiev and Botoucharov, 2007).

DATA AND METHODS

The burial history and basin modeling of the Tarnovo depression is based on geological and geophysical information of 15 deep well sections, using the popular geological time scale of Harland *et al.* (1990). The lithological, log and geochemical data on the Lower–Middle Jurassic intervals, and especially the enriched in organic matter Stefanets Member, are taken from previous studies (Georgiev and Dabovski, 1997; Georgiev, 1998, 2000; Botoucharov *et al.*, 2015, 2016, 2020, 2022). The results from the investigation of tens of samples were used for modeling the complex thermal evolution and hydrocarbon generation plots and diagrams.

The well sections of R-1 Resen, R-1 Momin Sbor, R-1 Burya, R-2 Kozarevets, and R-4 Dragizhevo were chosen for modeling of the tectonic and basin subsidence as well as the heat flow and hydrocarbon generation history (Figs 3–6). They were selected as key points for modeling because of their location and thick Lower–Middle Jurassic sedimentary sequences. The modeling of these wells and the Stefanets Member as a source rock horizon allows to characterize the thermal and generation history of perspective sediments in the Tarnovo depression.

The free PDI-1D software of IES, Julich, was used to reconstruct the development of hydrocarbon generation history of the Stefanets Member source rocks. The measured vitrinite reflectance was used as calibration points for the computer-calculated trends of vitrinite reflectance, following the kinetic “Easy %R” algorithm (Sweeney and Burnham,

1990). The chosen kinetic parameters are adapted for kerogen types II and III (*sensu* Tissot and Espitalié, 1975).

TECTONIC AND BASIN SUBSIDENCE

The Mesozoic development of the southern deeply buried part of the Moesian Platform was significantly influenced by the synsedimentary nature of the formed normal faults. The structure and depositional setting in the Tarnovo depression were typical for a platform marginal extensional basin initiated, developed, and then ceased during the Early–Middle Jurassic (Georgiev and Botoucharov, 2007). The study area belongs to a west–east elongated basin, which mainly covers the western and central parts of the South Moesian Platform margin. Early Jurassic rifting strongly affected the periphery of the southern Moesian Platform and induced fault disruption, with a system of growth faults and tilted blocks formed at this time. The South Moesian growth fault acted as the main north-bounding

border fault between the Moesian Platform and its subsided margin (Fig. 1). This border fault limited the northern distribution of the thick Lower–Middle Jurassic deposits. The fault has a 900 m amplitude in the Triassic and Lower–Middle Jurassic sediments, and in the Upper Jurassic–Valanginian complex it is of the order of 350 m in the study area. In well R-1 Resen, the Lower–Middle Jurassic sediments are 539 m thick, while just 3.5 km north of the fault, in R-10 Resen, there are only 28 m of Middle Jurassic rocks of the Esenitsa Formation. Southward, several tectonic structures, such as the Samovodene–Antonovo and Lyaskovets faults, demonstrate also growth development during the Early–Middle Jurassic and decisively influenced the depositional environment. The basin bathymetry is controlled by the subsidence rate, which is greater along the main growth faults, and the reconstruction of tectonic and basin subsidence is very important.

Subsidence curves were obtained from the data of selected well sections after PDI-1D computer modeling (Fig. 3). The results characterize the variations in the subsidence of the basin sediments after

Fig. 3. a) Tectonic subsidence modeling of three selected wells in the study area; b) Observed basement/base and backstripped tectonic subsidence of the selected wells from NE to SW. Line I–II shown in Fig. 1b–d).

the accretion of each horizon from the Triassic to the present day and outline the trends in the Mesozoic–Neozoic development in the studied area. Tectonic subsidence curves distinguish zones of slow subsidence and periods of relatively rapid subsidence interrupted by tectonic quiescence or uplift of the sedimentary base. According to the concepts of lithospheric extension and rifting of McKenzie (1978) and Wernicke (1985), phases of increased subsidence correspond to episodes of active tectonics, which in the South Moesian Platform margin is mainly related to the timing of extension. The flat or ascending parts of the curves account for periods of compression, erosion, and/or no sedimentation.

The tectonic subsidence, excluding the influence of sedimentary loading by “backstripping” calculations (van Hinte, 1978), for the modeled locations is presented in Fig. 3a. The wells were selected in order to provide optimal territory coverage in the study area, as well as to clearly illustrate the change in tectonic subsidence from northeast to southwest along the line I-II (Fig. 1). The total tectonic subsidence accumulated in the course of the geodynamic development for each individual location shows that it is the least in well R-1 Resen and the largest in R-1 Burya. The analysis of the curves in Fig. 3a. shows that an important role was played by the tectonic subsidence during the Early and Middle Jurassic, related to the extensional processes at that time. The contribution of only the tectonic factor to the subsidence in the study area varies and can be estimated by comparing the tectonic subsidence with the basin subsidence for the three boreholes from NE to SW (Fig. 3b–d). Tectonic subsidence accounted for about 40% of the total basin subsidence during the Early–Middle Jurassic. In well R-1 Resen, the quantitative tectonic subsidence for the indicated period was estimated at 226 m, and in the southwest it increases to about 300 m in R-1 Momin Sbor and up to 400 m in R-1 Burya. The latter well location falls into the area immediately overlain by the Balkanide Thrust Belt, which has resulted in bending of the basin floor by the advancing belt, greater tectonic and basin subsidence, and deposition of a thicker Lower–Middle Jurassic section. Therefore, the amplitude of subsidence during the Early–Middle Jurassic is largely a consequence of tectonic processes in an extensional basin with tilted, fault-bounded, and eventually rotated blocks.

The trend of an increasing tectonic and basin subsidence in a southward direction is clearly observed from well R-1 Resen toward R-1 Burya (Fig. 3b–d). The increase in subsidence is evident during the extensional period in the Early–Middle Juras-

sic and during the advancement of the Balkanides from the south. Late Cretaceous–Quaternary basin subsidence resulted primarily from sediment deposition rather than any significant tectonic processes. The detailed analysis of the sediment burial and thickness of the complexes in all wells in the study area outlines a slight increase in tectonic subsidence from the east to the west.

THERMAL CALIBRATION AND MODELING

The computer maturity model of the deposited sediments in depth for the selected borehole sections was built based on the measured borehole temperatures and vitrinite reflectances, which were used to calibrate and confirm its validity (Fig. 4a). Numbered events represent the individual lithostratigraphic units ordered from the oldest horizon reached by drilling (lowest numbered), following the sedimentation sequence to the youngest horizon (highest numbered). The obtained trends for the variation of the temperatures and reflectivity are represented by lines that optimally cover the measured values, and the deviations are within the frame of the acceptable error. There is a clear increase in maturity with depth and from the north to the south.

The change in temperature, the vitrinite reflectances and the heat flow are modeled according to the geodynamic evolution in the study area (Fig. 4b). The maturity measurements in investigated wells serve as a calibration parameter for defining the magnitude of heat flows for the different geological periods and epochs. The heat flow history of the South Moesian Platform Margin, and the Tarnovo depression as its integral part, is difficult to determine because of the complicated geodynamic evolution of the region. The margin was repeatedly affected by several Mesozoic rifting cycles, interrupted and followed by compressional events. These processes controlled the maturity of sediments and related the hydrocarbon generation. The 1D modeling approach allows the applied heat flow to be consistent with burial and thermal history in the Tarnovo depression. In this case, extensional periods are distinguished and temporally limited, allowing differential lithosphere stretching and heating. A more complicated and realistic scenario was used to determine the heat flow values, which take into account the extensional periods during the Mesozoic. The applied heat flow model includes elevated temperatures only for the Late Permian–Early Triassic and Early–Middle Jurassic rift phases because of the deep pre-Jurassic erosion. These extensional

Fig. 4. a) Measured and calculated temperature and vitrinite reflectance trends in selected wells in the study area; b) Temperature, vitrinite reflectance and heat flow distribution during the geological evolution in the study area.

periods are characterized by high heat flow up to 80 mW/m² for different zones in the study area and slightly higher for the southern ones. Thermal relaxation between rifting is also assumed. Until the deposition of the Upper Jurassic–Lower Cretaceous sediments, there was not sufficient thickness for the thermal maturation of the Lower–Middle Jurassic complex and the magnitude of heating was not decisive. The model rejects values above 50–60 mW/m² after the Late Cimmerian orogeny, because they overestimate the measured %Ro. Therefore, the constant heat flow of 50 mW/m² is applied afterwards. The heat flow and thermal maturity distribution during the geological history was a consequence of the higher sedimentation rate from the north to the south, confirmed by modeled sections in wells R-2 Kozarevets, R-1 Momin Sbor and R-4 Dragizhevo.

BURIAL HISTORY AND HYDROCARBON GENERATION MODEL

The analysis of the thermal history of the study area is an important element in estimating hydrocarbon generation from prospective rocks. The subsidence of the sediments leads to their maturation and conversion of organic matter to hydrocarbons. The burial history and thermal maturity of the organic matter determines whether the sedimentary rocks have generated, are generating, or will generate oil and gas under favorable thermodynamic conditions. Analyzing the thermal indicators, determining the heat flow, and detailing the geodynamic development of the sedimentary basin, allowed to trace the processes of hydrocarbon generation over geological time and in the spatial framework.

The Lower–Middle Jurassic sediments are recognized by their lithological variety and considerable thickness up to 800 m in the study area (Fig. 2). The Middle Jurassic (Aalenian–lower Bajocian) dark silty shales and siltstones belong to the Stefanets Member from the lower part of the Etropole Formation, and are considered to have been deposited in shallow to deep marine settings (Sapunov and Tchoumatchenco, 1989; Georgiev and Botoucharov, 2007; Sapunov and Metodiev, 2009; Georgiev et al., 2022). The thickness of the Stefanets Member also varies in broad range but is up to 60 m in the Tarnovo depression and rarely exceeds 200 m in the Moesian Platform. Where the total Lower–Middle Jurassic (mainly the Ozirovo and Etropole formations) thickness increases considerably in the southern parts of the Moesian Platform, the source

rocks with higher organic matter content have good potential for hydrocarbon generation.

Recently, core and outcrop samples from the Middle Jurassic Stefanets Member (Etropole Formation), consisting mainly of shale enriched in organic matter, were an object for the detailed geochemical investigations in the central south Moesian Platform, eastern part of the Western Fore-Balkan and western part of the Balkan orogenic system (Botoucharov *et al.*, 2015, 2016, 2020, 2022). Rock Eval analyzed intervals show very good source quantity and quality. TOC values usually vary between 0.70% and 2.00% in some cases and more. The kerogen types II and II/III indicate marine organic matter and oil-gas prone potential. Therefore, the Stefanets Member, as the most perspective source rocks in the Lower–Middle Jurassic sequence, is the key interval in the presented complex burial and hydrocarbon generation model.

The burial history versus the reconstructed thermal maturity trends presented by vitrinite reflectance lines are illustrated for the selected wells in Fig. 5. Because of the similar results, in spite of some differences in drilled sections, the northern part of the study area is characterized by wells R-1 Resen and R-2 Kozarevets. To the south towards the platform margin, the rocks are deeply buried, presented by the models of wells R-1 Momin Sbor and R-4 Dragizhevo.

The realization of the petroleum potential from the Lower–Middle Jurassic rocks in well R-1 Resen started in the Early Cretaceous (Fig. 5, upper left side). The deposits enter the “oil window” in the late Barremian, starting active generation in the middle Aptian when all the Lower–Middle Jurassic formations (events shaded in gray in Fig. 5) are in early mature and, at the end of the Late Cretaceous, reaching peak mature stage.

In well R-2 Kozarevets to the southeast, there are a few million years of speedup, although there is the same middle Aptian active hydrocarbon generation (Fig. 5, upper right side). The only difference from the situation in Resen is that the lower part of the Lower–Middle Jurassic rocks reached the late mature stage in the mid-Paleogene.

Farther to the south and southeast, in wells R-4 Dragizhevo and R-1 Momin Sbor, the burial history and maturity trends reflect the deeper subsidence of the sediments (Fig. 5, lower side). The Lower–Middle Jurassic rocks (events shaded in gray in Fig. 5) enter the “oil window” earlier, in the Hauterivian or even the late Valanginian, continuously passing through early, peak and late mature stages. Finally, the few tens or hundreds of meters of the bottom

Fig. 5. Burial history of the selected well sections and maturity stages in depth and time. The events on the charts covering the Early–Middle Jurassic time span and depth intervals are shaded.

Lower–Middle Jurassic sequence enter the postmature stage with gas generation from the end of the Early Cretaceous.

The hydrocarbon generation history just from the Stefanets Member (source rocks with higher organic matter content) in the study area is modeled and presented in Fig. 6. The model of R-2 Kozarevetz shows that there is a peak of the oil generation in the Albian and liquid generation is still in progress. The thermogenic gas generation is not an option, because the Middle Jurassic sediments in

this area are not too deeply buried, but there is still possible small gas condensate release.

The models of wells R-1 Momin Sbor and R-4 Dragizhevo are also demonstrated in Fig. 6. The highest temperatures are reached at the end of the Aptian for applied heat flow scenario, when the maximum burial happened. Because of the kerogen type, high maturity and increased basin subsidence, both diagrams illustrate the peak of the oil generation at the end of the Barremian. Gas generation started in the Barremian and continued during the Cenozoic.

Fig. 6. Model of the heat flow, temperature, vitrinite reflectance and hydrocarbon generation for selected wells since the deposition of the Stefanets Member in the study area.

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CONCLUSION

The Tarnovo depression was developed mainly during the Early–Middle Jurassic and the sedimentation lasted until the late Bathonian, when the mid-Cimmerian orogeny culminated. The geological and depositional settings in the Tarnovo depression during the late Aalenian–early Bajocian were favorable for the accumulation of deeper-water sediments, including the mainly shales of the Stefanets Member.

The amplitude of subsidence during the Early–Middle Jurassic is largely a result of tectonic processes in an extensional basin with tilted, fault-bounded, and eventually rotated blocks. The observed trend in the modeled well sections argues for an increasing tectonic and basin subsidence in a southward direction.

The applied heat flow model includes elevated temperatures for extensional phases in the Late Permian–Early Triassic and Early–Middle Jurassic. The heat flow is up to 80 mW/m² for the mentioned time periods and is slightly higher for southern zones in the study area. The constant heat flow of 50 mW/m² is applied after the Late Cimmerian orogeny.

The Lower–Middle Jurassic sediments have a considerable thickness of up to 800 m in the study area. These rocks entered the “oil window” in the late Barremian, Hauterivian or even in the late Valanginian towards the south, starting active generation in the middle Aptian. The model shows that gas generation is possible only in the southern and marginal zones of the Tarnovo depression. Among the sequence, the Stefanets Member of the Etropole Formation is composed of shales and siltstones, deposited in a relatively deep-marine setting in the Tarnovo depression. The evaluated intervals show good source rock quantity and quality. The kerogen types II and II/III indicate marine organic matter and oil-gas prone potential.

The model of the northern well sections shows that there is a peak of oil generation from the Stefanets Member in the Albian and oil generation is still in progress. The model for the southern wells argues for peak of the oil generation at the end of the Barremian, and then gas generation took place.

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